

DELAMINATION BUCKLING: NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF EXPERIMENTS

M. König, J. Albinger and C. Hänsel

Institute for Statics and Dynamics of Aerospace Structures, Director Prof. Dr.-Ing. B. Kröplin
University of Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 27, Stuttgart 80, Germany

ABSTRACT

The growth of delaminations near the surface of laminated CFRP-specimens during tension-compression fatigue loading has been studied by measuring the out-of-plane (i.e. buckling) deformation of the delaminated region via moiré technique. From the measured deformations the delamination front contours have been determined. The postbuckling state of the specimens in the compression phase of the test, which is assumed to drive the delamination growth, can be computed by a two-dimensional (plate) finite element model in which the measured delamination front contour is taken into account. First results for the computed displacements of a specimen with artificial circular delamination, as used as starter-delamination in the tests, show satisfactory agreement with the measured deformation. The goal of the investigations is, to compute energy release rates along measured delamination front contours and to correlate the results with the measured delamination growth.

Keywords: Delamination Buckling, Moiré Interferometry, Finite Element Analysis,
Delamination Growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

Realisation of the full potential of composites depends upon the maintenance of composite structures in in-use situations. This leads to the requirement, that the growth of detected delaminations due to service load conditions within an inspection interval should be predictable. For studying the growth of delaminations in CFRP (Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic) - laminates experiments have been performed by applying tension-compression fatigue loading to specimens containing an artificial circular delamination near the specimen-surface. By measuring the out-of-plane deformation of the laminated region, the development of the delamination front contour could be determined. This has been achieved by measuring the deformation of the specimen in the postbuckling state of the delaminated sublaminates via a moiré technique and then postprocessing the digitized pictures. The obtained delamination front contours can be included in a finite element

model of the specimen, from which the energy release rates along the delamination front can be computed. It is anticipated that by a correlation of these results with the measured development of the delamination front contour a law for delamination growth due to periodic local buckling of the sublaminat can be derived.

2. EVALUATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS

The experiments have been carried out with a CFRP-laminate, made from continuous carbonfibre-reinforced epoxy using a stacking sequence of $[\pm 5/+45/\pm 5/-45/0/\pm 85/0/-45/\mp 5/+45/\mp 5]$. Artificial circular delaminations have been introduced at interface 2/3 during the fabrication process by embedding a double foil from a 20 μm thick release film, as in ¹. An antibuckling guide with rectangular window was clamped to the test specimens (Figures 1, 2) suppressing global buckling of the specimen. Loading frequency was 10 Hz at $R=-1$ with constant stress amplitudes of 220-240 MPa for specimens with 10 mm width of the initial delamination and 180-200 MPa for specimens with 20 mm delamination width. These stress amplitudes have shown to yield stable delamination growth.

The principle of the optical in-situ technique for measuring out-of-plane displacements of a surface is illustrated in Figure 3. When two repetitious patterns deform relatively to each other a moiré effect is observed, resulting in a fringe pattern. During measurement procedure the object surface is illuminated with a grid pattern produced by a Michelson interferometer, which is monitored and digitized by a CCD-video camera. Due to the specific frame time (40 ms) of the CCD-camera it is necessary to stop dynamic loading and to monitor the test specimen at two static load levels. The difference of the two phase patterns results in a phase distribution representing the buckling shape of the delaminated region. From this the out-of-plane displacements can be obtained in the form of an intensity distribution which can be figured in gray levels of constant displacements (Figure 4). Extracting cross-sections out of the gray level distribution yields an appropriate model of the displacement field (Figures 5, 6).

In Figure 6, region I is the ascending part of the cross-section curve containing displacements of sublaminat raising up from plane stage in unloaded mode. The slope of the displacements is opposite to deformation in region II which is dominated by the deformation of the basic laminate. The set of points in each region resulting from the image processing was condensed by least square fit. The delamination front contour was then computed by assuming that the intersection of the fitted curves coincides with the delamination edge. The accuracy of this approach was checked by comparison with X-ray radiography. It is found (compare Figure 7 with Figure 8 and Figure 9 with Figure 10) that there exists still a systematic discrepancy, depending on the smoothness of the transition from the sublaminat buckling to the base-laminate deformation and due to possible crack surface closing, as found in the numerical simulation. On the other hand, the progression of the delamination front (i.e. the difference of two subsequent contours) is obtained rather accurately. The error in the determination of the position of the delamination edge can be reduced by a more sophisticated image processing and the error due to crack surface closure can be accounted for in the finite element model by an iterative procedure, controlled by comparison of measured and computed sublaminat displacements.

3. NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS

First finite element analyses have been performed with the goal to finally compute energy release rate distributions along the delamination front contours. Four-noded quadrilateral layered plate elements, which allow transverse shear deformation² have been employed for this purpose. The (partly) delaminated plate was modeled by two subplates with the nodes located at the plane of delamination over the whole region modeled, which is the region inside of the window of the antibuckling guide. A penetration of the two subplates within the delaminated area was prevented by a contact processor that utilizes a contactor target concept applying the penalty method^{3,4}. The material stiffness of the two subplates was computed according to classical laminate theory. The nonlinear compression-load displacement computation along the load path of Figure 11 was performed by Newton-Raphsen iteration, employing the total Lagrange formulation. To bypass the bifurcation point L in Figure 11 small additional lateral forces have been applied at load levels near the bifurcation point. The bifurcation point itself was computed by a linear buckling analysis in advance.

The results obtained for a specimen in the initial state, with an artificial delamination of diameter 10 mm, are presented in Figure 12 and Figure 13. For comparison the deformations measured for different load levels of applied average compressive stress have been added. It is found that the boundary conditions applied to boundary of the modeled region, which has been chosen identical to the boundary of the window of the antibuckling guide (Figures 1, 2), has no influence on the computed deformation within the bounds of the loads for which stable delamination growth occurs in the tests (i.e. 220-240 N/mm² for 10 mm initial delamination width). This has been checked by applying first a clamped and then a simply supported condition. The same holds for the value for the linear buckling load for sublaminar buckling σ_L . Comparing the computed displacements with those measured during a quasi-static test and during the first load cycle of the fatigue tests in Figure 12 shows, that the computed displacements for 10 mm delamination width are considerably smaller than those which have been measured. However, it was found by X-ray radiography that it is likely possible that the effective delamination width is larger than the width of the embedded release film (up to about 11 mm). This results from relative movement of the two release foils, occurring during the manufacturing process. Assuming a delamination with a diameter of 11 mm for the finite element model yields much better agreement with the test results. However, the results of the quasi-static test in Figure 12 show a rather large imperfection of the buckling situation. The reason for this can be either the finite thickness of the embedded double release foil (40 μ m), which has been neglected in the finite element model, or a very loose fitting of the specimen into the antibuckling guide. These points will be investigated further.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown, that the buckling of the sublaminar of specimens with embedded delamination can be simulated rather well by two-dimensional plate finite element models. The next step will be to compute the energy release rates along the delamination front with the goal to derive a criterion for delamination growth.

Acknowledgement

The work is supported by the *Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft* (Az.: Kr 668/17-1)

References

1. Bergmann, H.W. et al., *Mechanical Properties and Damage Mechanisms of Carbonfibre-Reinforced Composites*, DFVLR Institut für Strukturmechanik, DFVLR-FB-88-41, 1988.
2. Parisch, H., *An Investigation of a Finite Rotation Four Node Assumed Strain Shell Element*, Int. J. Num. Meth. Eng., Vol. 31, pp. 127 - 150, 1991.
3. Parisch, H., *A Consistent Tangent Stiffness Matrix for Three-Dimensional Non-Linear Contact Analysis*, Int. J. Num. Meth. Eng., Vol. 28, pp. 1803 - 1812, 1989.
4. Parisch, H., *NOVA - User Manual*, Institute for Statics and Dynamics of Aerospace Structures, University of Stuttgart, 1992.

Figure 1: Test specimen with antibuckling guide

Figure 2: Test specimen

Figure 3: Principle of measurement by moiré technique

Figure 4: Out-of-plane displacements

Figure 5: Pseudo-3D-plot of displacements

Figure 6: Two typical cross-sections of out-of-plane displacements

Figure 7: X-ray photograph of delamination after 200000 load cycles

Figure 8: Propagation of delamination up to 200000 load cycles

Figure 9: X-ray photograph of delamination after 500 000 load cycles

Figure 10: Propagation of delamination up to 500 000 load cycles

Figure 11: Pattern of the load displacement curve of the centre of the sublaminates

Figure 12: Comparison of experimentally determined displacements with FE-results

Figure 13: Measured and computed buckling deformations at different load-levels (Deformation magnified)